

Strategic Bidding of Retailers in Wholesale Energy Markets: A Model Using Hybrid Forecast Methods

Hugo Algarvio and Fernando Lopes

LNEG—National Laboratory of Energy and Geology
Est. Paço do Lumiar 22, Lisbon, Portugal
{hugo.algarvio,fernando.lopes}@lneg.pt

Abstract. The liberalization of the electricity sector brought wholesale and retail competition to electricity markets. In the retail sector, different retailers compete to sign bilateral contracts with consumers. Typically, retailers consider high premiums to cover their potential risks when acquiring energy in wholesale markets. This paper proposes a model for strategic bidding of retailers in wholesale markets. The model includes several hybrid forecast methods, namely a multivariate time series for long-term prediction of electricity prices and consumption, a historical meteorological comparison of consumption to day-ahead forecast, and short-run trends for intra-day forecast of consumption. The paper also presents a case study where retailers with different risk attitudes submit bids to the spot market to satisfy their consumers. The results show that bidding to short-term markets leads to lower forecast errors than bidding to medium- and long-term markets. Furthermore, retailers with large and varied portfolios of customers may have lower forecast errors than retailers with small portfolios of customers.

Keywords: Electricity markets; Retailer entities; Strategic bidding; Risk management; Forecast methods; Portfolios of consumers.

1 Introduction

The deregulation of the electricity industry brings competition to the energy supply in both wholesale and retail sectors [1]. Market entities can trade electricity at wholesale markets, bilateral markets and non-organised markets [2]. In wholesale markets, they can submit bids to day-ahead and intraday (sub-) markets. Real-time deviations from the schedules of balance responsible parties (BRPs) need to be managed at balancing markets [3]. BRPs may have to pay/receive the down/up balancing costs, which normally results in penalties. In bilateral markets, participants can sign standard financial and physical contracts to hedge against spot price volatility (and consumption uncertainty), reducing their risk. For non-standard agreements, they can negotiate privately the terms and conditions of bilateral contracts [4, 5].

Retailers can sign private bilateral contracts with end-use consumers, thus obtaining a private portfolio to manage. They usually follow a business as usual strategy, considering high risk premiums in their proposed tariffs. These risk premiums depend on the risk attitude of retailers (also known as risk preference or appetite), which can be characterized as risk-averse, risk-neutral or risk-seeking (see, e.g., [6, 7]).

To avoid losses, a major issue that retailers should consider when proposing tariffs to consumers is the forecast of market prices. The dynamic of the portfolios is very dependent of the meteorological conditions, the consumption days (weekdays, holidays or weekends), and the type of consumers (residential, commercial, industrial, etc.). So, minimizing the variability of the portfolios can be a good solution to avoid high forecast errors, which can result in unbalances, and consequently in the payment of penalties. Short-run strategic bidding is often considered crucial to retailers, since bilateral transactions are usually made in the long-run (months before real-time consumption).

Ayón *et al.* [8] pointed out that large and varied portfolios of consumers may reduce demand forecast errors. The authors also stated that aggregations of flexible demand are beneficial to reduce demand forecast errors, increasing the return of aggregators. Wei *et al.* [9] presented a review of 128 forecast models for energy demand. They indicated a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of 10% as the threshold for highly accurate forecasts. They concluded that small-scale forecasts (e.g., small consumers) have larger errors than large-scale forecasts (e.g., large consumers). Koponen *et al.* [10] presented a review of 12 models to forecast short-term electricity demand. They used the models in 6 different scenarios. They concluded that the normalized root mean square error (NRMSE) of the forecasts decreases with the number of aggregated consumers. They also stated that hybrid methods should be used to compute demand forecasts.

Against this background, this paper focuses on developing a strategic bidding model for retailers participating in spot markets, aiming at reducing forecast errors, and consequently unbalances and penalties, increasing the return. The work presented here refines and extends our previous work on portfolio optimization [6, 7, 11], electricity markets [3], and risk management [12, 13].

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 presents an overview of bilateral contracting, risk management and portfolio optimization. Section 3 introduces a model for strategic bidding of retailers. Section 4 presents a case study. Finally, concluding remarks are presented in section 5.

2 Risk Management and Portfolio Optimization

Sellers and buyers of electricity negotiate bilateral contracts to hedge against spot price volatility. Their attitude towards risk can be classified as risk-averse, risk-neutral, and risk-seeking. They consider different utility functions according to their risk attitude [12]. Typically, they follow a risk management process involving three main phases: risk assessment, risk characterization and risk mitigation.

Retailers want to optimize the risk-return output of their portfolios by taking into account their attitude towards risk. They sign customized contracts with key consumers and select the best market options to purchase electricity. In [6], we proposed an optimization model that can be used to select key consumers for portfolios of retailers, using the aforementioned three phases of the risk management process, as well as a risk-return optimization of the portfolios and the Markowitz theory, in order to obtain the efficient frontier that optimizes the portfolios. In the first phase, retailers face the following risk factors: market price volatility and consumption uncertainty of portfolios. In the second phase, retailers can use the VaR to verify how the previous risk factors can affect their potential return. In the third phase, by adopting the optimization problem described in [6], they can obtain the point that optimizes their risk-return ratio (consisting in a share of consumers in their portfolios), considering their risk attitude and the tariffs proposed to consumers.

The Markowitz efficient frontier is obtained by considering the conditions of the markets defined in the first phase of the risk management process, the risk analysis carried out in the second phase (e.g., using VaR), and the optimized points obtained in the third phase. Retailers obtain the efficient frontier from the different efficient points (a specific point is considered efficient if no other point can surpass its result in terms of risk or return).

The electricity tariff is essentially a two-part tariff with a fixed payment for power (contracted capacity) and a price per unit of used electricity (variable fee). Both fees are divided into several parts, but the part that may give a return to retailers is the energy part [6]. So, retailers can set a return tax for each consumer, according to the sum of the risk-free (deposits) of the global markets with the risk premium. The risk premium depends on several factors (e.g., the risk associated with the market price volatility and the consumption uncertainty).

In [6], we also presented several pricing strategies to be adopted by retailers to negotiate with consumers. The strategies can be selected by considering the type of tariff (single, dual, three-rate, etc.), the equality of tariff (personalized or not), the equality of return (if every consumer gives a similar return to retailer), etc. The “Equal Return OPTimization” (EROP) strategy defines the minimum tariff that retailers may offer to consumers to receive an equal target return from each of them. The “Equal Tariff Optimization strategy at a Minimum Return” (ETOMinR) is not personalized, considering the same tariff for all consumers. Retailers compute a tariff to each consumer and select the highest one because it guarantees that they receive the minimum target return. The “Equal Tariff Optimization at a Maximum Return” (ETOMaxR) strategy is also not personalized. To guarantee a maximum target return from all consumers, retailers compute a tariff to each consumer, and the minimum tariff (between all computed) is selected, because it guarantees that retailers receive their target maximum return. The “Equal Return Tariff based on Market-Costs” (ERTMC) strategy reflects the expected costs of retailers with each consumer, considering their consumption pattern [7].

The Calinski-Harabasz (CH) criterion computes the Euclidean distance between different clusters and compares it with the internal sum of squared errors for each cluster. K-means clustering is a robust technique that minimizes the distance between each point and the centre of its respective cluster [7]. Considering the consumption profile of each consumer, and using the CH criterion, it is possible to obtain the optimal number of profiles (clusters). Furthermore, by using K-means clustering, it is possible to divide consumers by profile. Each cluster represents the consumption segment of each consumer, with a typical load profile.

Future predictions of the arithmetic cost of electricity for each consumer are computed by considering a forecast method adapted from [6]. The method consists of a Multivariate Time series (MTS) that uses the wholesale market prices of electricity, the electricity consumption, and the share of renewable energy associated with the production of electricity. Also, future predictions of the electricity consumption are computed by using an MTS forecast method adapted from [7].

Now, by considering the optimization model and the pricing strategies, it is possible to compute the expected return of retailers for long periods of time. However, retailers need to submit bids to wholesale markets based on power forecasts, which can lead to power deviations and penalties during real-time operation. The next section discusses the strategic bidding of retailers in wholesale markets, in order to reduce the errors of consumption forecasts and their effects on the final return.

3 Strategic Bidding in Wholesale Markets

Retailers can submit bids to wholesale markets or enter into bilateral agreements to acquire energy from producers and other suppliers. As BRPs, they are responsible for their deviations, meaning that their imbalances need to be compensated in balancing markets. Also, the day-ahead market (DAM) can be used to obtain/sell the need/excess of electricity. Furthermore, the intra-day market (IDM) can be used to compensate potential short-run imbalances.

Retailers select the past day, \hat{D} , with the minimum Euclidean distance, d , between the historical weather data of a particular past day, W_{D-i} , and the weather forecast of the target day, \hat{W}_D , considering one or more weather sensitive variables (e.g., humidity or ambient temperature).

$$\hat{D} = \min(d(\hat{W}_D, W_{D-i})) \quad (1)$$

Retailers compute the expected consumption, $\hat{q}_{j,D}$, by getting the consumption of the past day, $q_{j,\hat{D}}$, and considering the consumption forecast of the current year, \hat{q}_t , as well as the consumption of the past year q_{t-1} :

$$\hat{q}_{j,D} = q_{j,\hat{D}} \frac{\hat{q}_t}{q_{t-1}} \quad (2)$$

To forecast the yearly electricity consumption, retailers use an MTS method adapted from [7]. They compute the (hourly) consumption forecast of the portfolio, $\hat{q}_{D,h}$, by considering the forecast, $\hat{q}_{j,D,h}$, of each consumer c_j for each time period h of day D :

$$\hat{q}_{D,h} = \sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^J \hat{q}_{j,D,h} \quad (3)$$

Retailers determine the bids to submit to the DAM by considering the energy involved in the entire portfolio $q_{0,h}$. For each time period, they may consider several contracts Ct . The total quantity of electricity guaranteed through bilateral contracts is denoted as $q_{c,h}$, so that:

$$q_{0,h} = \hat{q}_{D,h} - q_{c,h} \quad (4)$$

$$q_{c,h} = \sum_{ct=1}^{Ct} q_{c_{ct},h} \quad (5)$$

For a particular time period of the day, if the quantity of electricity guaranteed through bilateral contracts is higher than the energy forecasted, $\hat{q}_{D,h}$, then retailers try to sell the excess in the intra-day market. To this end, the bids are computed by using a simple strategy: in the case of buying electricity, retailers offer the price-cap (maximum price) of the market, to guarantee that they buy the required electricity to satisfy their portfolio; otherwise, they offer the price of the bilateral contracts, to avoid economic losses.

Retailers compute the consumption forecast, $\hat{q}_{s,j,h}$, for bidding at each session of the intra-day market s , by using a method that takes into account the meteorological conditions and the short-run consumption tendency, as well as the bids submitted to the DAM and the growth-rate method for a short-run period of 1h–7h:

$$\hat{q}_{s,j,h} = \hat{q}_{s,j,h-1} \left(\sum_{h=1}^H \sum_{j=1}^J \frac{\hat{q}_{j,D,h}}{\hat{q}_{j,D,h-1}} \right) \quad (6)$$

This formula considers the real observed consumption of the previous time period, if it exists, or the forecast, $\hat{q}_{s,j,h-1}$. For each consumer j and time period h , it uses the bids submitted to the DAM at h (i.e., $\hat{q}_{j,D,h}$), and also at a previous time period, $\hat{q}_{j,D,h-1}$.

Retailers compute the bids to submit to each intra-day session, $q_{s,h}$, at time period, h , by considering the short-run forecast, as well as the electricity acquired through bilateral contracts, $q_{c,h}$, through the DAM, $q_{0,h}$, and in previous intra-day sessions, $q_{i,h}$:

$$q_{s,h} = \hat{q}_{j,h} - q_{c,h} - q_{0,h} - \sum_{i=1}^{s-1} q_{i,h} \quad (7)$$

They compute the imbalances for each time period, $q_{dev,h}$, by taking into account the real-time consumption of each consumer of the portfolio, $q_{j,h}$:

$$q_{dev,h} = \sum_{j=1}^J q_{j,h} - q_{c,h} - q_{0,h} - \sum_{s=1}^S q_{s,h} \quad (8)$$

Also, they compute their balance responsibility for each time period, $C_{dev,h}$, by considering their deviations, $q_{dev,h}$ and the prices of the excess, $P_{up,h}$, or the lack, $P_{down,h}$, of electricity, in cases of up or down deviations, respectively.

$$\begin{cases} C_{dev,h} = q_{dev,h}P_{up,h}, & \text{for } q_{dev,h} > 0 \\ C_{dev,h} = |q_{dev,h}|P_{down,h}, & \text{for } q_{dev,h} < 0 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Different bilateral contracts may have different prices for the energy. A contract ct has price, $P_{ct,h}$, and the investment, I_h , of retailers is:

$$I_h = \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{ct=1}^{Ct} P_{ct,h}q_{ct,h} + P_{0,h}q_{0,h} + \sum_{s=1}^S P_{s,h}q_{s,h} - C_{dev,h} \quad (10)$$

The profit per time period of retailers and the return on investment (ROI) are computed as follows:

$$R_h = \sum_{j=1}^J T_{j,h}q_{j,h} - \sum_{ct=1}^{Ct} P_{ct,h}q_{ct,h} + P_{0,h}q_{0,h} + \sum_{s=1}^S P_{s,h}q_{s,h} - C_{dev,h} \quad (11)$$

$$ROI = \sum_{h=1}^H \frac{R_h}{I_h} \quad (12)$$

The ROI is a performance indicator that allows to measure the profitability of investments.

To evaluate the performance of the forecast techniques, two different indicators, MAPE and NRMSE, are used:

$$MAPE = \frac{100\%}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H \left| \frac{q_h - \hat{q}_h}{q_h} \right| \quad (13)$$

$$NRMSE = 100\% \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{H} \sum_{h=1}^H (\hat{q}_h - q_h)^2}}{q_{max}} \quad (14)$$

where q_{max} is the maximum consumption per time period of the portfolio.

MAPE results are very intuitive, which makes this indicator one of the most used to measure forecasts accuracy. However, it has limitations, particularly it cannot be used with zero values and overestimates of negative errors ($\hat{q}_h > q_h$) concerning positive errors. NRMSE is used to evaluate energy forecasts. It overvalues high errors concerning low errors, which is often acceptable, due to the critical nature of the energy balance on power systems.

Table 1. Characteristics of retailers.

Retailer	Risk Preference	Pricing Strategy	Tariff Type	Number of Clients	Yearly Energy (GWh)	Expected ROI (%)	VaR (%)
<i>Ret₁</i>	High aversion	EROP	3-rate	5	2.76	3.75	3.42
<i>Ret₂</i>	Moderate averse	ETOMaxR	3-rate	22	475.17	3.95	3.78
<i>Ret₃</i>	Small aversion	EROP	Single	13	30.46	7.54	3.99
<i>Ret₄</i>	Small seeking	ERTMC	3-rate	32	290.99	7.3	4.13
<i>Ret₅</i>	Moderate seek	ETOMinR	3-rate	13	48.58	7.79	4.19
<i>Ret₆</i>	High seeking	ETOMinR	3-rate	227	917.03	9.95	4.59

4 Case study

This case study considers six computational agent retailers that want to invest in the Portuguese electricity market. The time period of the study ranges from January 1, 2012 to December 31, 2013.¹ The retailers are assumed to start operating at MIBEL in 2013, meaning that they can use real data from MIBEL. They have a target market of 312 real Portuguese consumers for their portfolios, corresponding to around 5% of the total consumption of the country [14]. Table 1 presents the main characteristics of each retailer, such as the expected ROI or VaR. The consumers are assumed to be connected to the middle voltage, so some of them are aggregations of residential and small commercial consumers. They are assumed to be divided into five segments: industrial (Ind), large commercial (LCom), aggregation of small commercials (AggSCom), aggregation of residentials (AggRES), and other aggregations.

Retailers propose customized bilateral contracts to consumers and, to satisfy their consumption needs, they acquire electricity on the wholesale market. The contracts involve either fixed single or three-rate tariffs, and variable consumption. The energy part of the tariff is the only part that can be negotiated. Retailers can offer personalized tariffs to different consumers or the same tariff to consumers inside the same consumption segment.

Retailers use an optimization model, adapted from [6], to obtain the optimized portfolios of end-use consumers, involving the Markowitz theory, pricing strategies, and risk/return objectives. To obtain the optimal portfolio for 2013, they use real market prices of 2012, updated with the forecasts for 2013, as well as real consumption from the target consumers from 2012, updated with forecasts for 2013. The forecast techniques presented in the previous section predicted a decrease in the wholesale market prices of 4.83% and an increase in consumption of 0.36%. This expected decrease in prices can be the result of an increase in the variable renewable generation with near-zero marginal costs.

¹ This data set can be found in an online repository: [#https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/ElectricityLoadDiagrams20112014\#](https://archive.ics.uci.edu/ml/datasets/ElectricityLoadDiagrams20112014).

Table 2. Results of the study using real data from 2013.

Retailer	Optimal ROI (%)	Real ROI (%)	Demand Variation (%)	DAM Bids (%)	DAM MAPE (%)	IDM Bids (%)	IDM Direction (%)	IDM MAPE (%)
<i>Ret₁</i>	6.82	5.09	-5.43	101.88	41.96	34.02	-3.18	23.24
<i>Ret₂</i>	7.25	5.96	-8.76	104.91	25.15	26.74	-10.05	15.73
<i>Ret₃</i>	12.21	11.10	-4.84	102.96	12.63	12.97	-16.15	8.73
<i>Ret₄</i>	12.35	11.62	-7.50	105.22	12.15	12.20	-43.45	7.25
<i>Ret₅</i>	10.10	9.15	-6.75	105.05	11.94	11.85	-36.87	7.21
<i>Ret₆</i>	12.18	11.67	-2.22	101.02	6.68	6.58	-23.90	3.49

Retailers enter into retail competition by offering tariffs to consumers, thus obtaining a private portfolio to manage.² In general, the optimized portfolios only suggest a small number of consumers (but see [7]). To increase that number, different constraints in the optimization model can be considered, such as the quantity of electricity or the investment.

To determine the bids to submit to the DAM, forecasts based on the expected weather of the following day are used, considering the ambient temperature (see Equation 1).³ Tables 2 and 3 present the results of the case-study. The results shown in Table 2 indicate that the real returns obtained through the strategic bidding process are higher than the expected returns, because the wholesale market prices decreased around 9.2%, from 2012 to 2013. Also, the consumption needs of all portfolios decreased. Such decreases led to retailers bidding the excess quantities of energy in the day-ahead market.

Retailers that have portfolios with few consumers have higher errors in their forecasts, being the versatility and complementarity between consumers a good solution to avoid errors. While *Ret₁* is the retailer with less risk, it is also the retailer with the highest forecast errors, because it is the retailer with fewer consumers. By comparing the real ROI with the optimal ROI, it is possible to verify that retailers with larger portfolios and lower forecast errors have lower differences in the ROI. Naturally, portfolios with a small number of consumers have substantial forecast errors. The forecast MAPE of *Ret₆* is in line with the forecast accuracy of highly accurate forecast models from the literature, validating the proposed forecast models [9]. The DAM forecast deviations can be fixed in the intra-day market, resulting in a traded quantity significantly lower than in the DAM.

² Tariffs proposed to target consumers, and their optimal and final portfolios, are presented in [15].

³ Day-ahead forecasts of the ambient temperature consider data from the Global Forecast System at 7 a.m. (CET). Observed and forecast meteorological data can be found at: <http://www.meteomanz.com/index?l=1>.

Table 3. Results of the study using real data from 2013 (cont.).

Retailer	Expected	Real	IR	DAM	DAM	IDM	IDM
	ROI (%)	ROI (%)	(%)	MAPE (%)	NRMSE (%)	MAPE (%)	NRMSE (%)
<i>Ret</i> ₁	3.75	5.09	35.73	41.96	13.16	23.24	10.41
<i>Ret</i> ₂	3.95	5.96	50.89	25.16	14.02	15.73	7.34
<i>Ret</i> ₃	7.54	11.10	47.21	12.63	8.25	8.73	4.54
<i>Ret</i> ₄	7.93	11.62	46.53	12.15	8.71	7.25	4.38
<i>Ret</i> ₅	7.79	9.15	17.59	11.94	7.67	7.21	4.36
<i>Ret</i> ₆	9.95	11.67	17.29	6.68	5.96	3.49	2.99

In 2013, the consumption decreases, leading retailers to trade the excess quantities of energy in the DAM (i.e., in the majority of hours, retailers sell the excess in the intra-day market). The forecast errors of the bids submitted to the intra-day market are lower due to the use of upgraded meteorological information (such as, data closer to real-time consumption). These errors need to be fixed in balancing markets. The intrinsic variation in the ROI computes the difference between the real ROI and the expected \hat{ROI} , evaluating the output of retailers as follows:

$$IR = \frac{ROI - \hat{ROI}}{\hat{ROI}} \times 100 \quad (15)$$

By analysing the IR, it is possible to verify that risk-seeking retailers have lower increases in their expected returns, which means that even with higher forecast errors, the portfolios of risk-averse retailers are more stable, leading to better outputs. Also, note that a decrease in energy consumption conducts to an excess of energy acquired in the DAM, leading to up deviations concerning real consumptions. Up deviations overvalues the MAPE, because real consumptions are lower than forecast consumptions in the majority of cases. In this way, the NRMSE can probably be a better indicator to evaluate the forecast results, by obtaining results that are independent of the deviation direction.

5 Conclusion

This article presented a simplified model for retailers trading energy in wholesale markets. The model considered three different hybrid forecast methods: a multivariate time series for long-term prediction of electricity prices and consumption, a historical meteorological comparison of consumption to day-ahead forecasts, and a short-run trend for intraday forecasts of consumption.

Also, the article presented a case study to test the model in a simple setting, considering real data from Portuguese consumers and the MIBEL, for the period 2012–2013. The results confirmed that large amounts of diversified aggregated demands conduct to higher forecast accuracies. Risk-seeking retailers have a behaviour similar to traditional retailers, considering large portfolios with substantial risk, and high risk premiums in their tariffs. Risk-seeking retailers propose more competitive tariffs than risk-averse retailers. However, risk-averse retailers may obtain a better output from electricity markets, even with higher demand forecast errors than risk-seeking retailers.

The main issues that retailers face in energy markets are the volatility of spot prices and the uncertainty in the energy needs of their portfolios. Accordingly, to mitigate the associated effects, they can propose more competitive tariffs to target consumers. Additionally, they can enter into bilateral contracts in the wholesale market and sign demand response contracts with consumers in retail markets.

Future work is intended to study how derivatives products, private bilateral contracts, and demand response programs can be used as risk mitigation instruments, (potentially) increasing the risk-return ratio of retailers.

References

1. Algarvio, H., Lopes, F., Couto, A., Estanqueiro, A., Santana, J.: Effects of regulating the European internal market on the integration of variable renewable energy. *WIREs Energy Environ* 2019;8(6):e346
2. Lopes, F., Coelho, H.: *Electricity Markets with Increasing Levels of Renewable Generation: Structure, Operation, Agent-based Simulation and Emerging Designs*, Springer, Cham, 2018.
3. Algarvio, H., Lopes, F., Couto, A., Estanqueiro, A.: Participation of Wind Power Producers in Day-ahead and Balancing Markets: An Overview and a Simulation-based Study. *WIREs Energy and Environment* 2019;8(5):e343.
4. Lopes, F., and Coelho, H.: *Concession Behaviour in Automated Negotiation*. In: *E-Commerce and Web Technologies*, Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg (2010)
5. Lopes, F., and Coelho, H.: *Concession Strategies for Negotiating Bilateral Contracts in Multi-agent Electricity Markets*. In: *23rd Database and Expert Systems Applications (DEXA 2012)*, pp. 321–325, IEEE (2012)
6. Algarvio, H., Lopes, F., Sousa, J., Lagarto, J.: Multi-agent electricity markets: Retailer portfolio optimization using Markowitz theory. *Electr Power Syst Res* 2017;148:282–94.
7. Algarvio, H., Lopes, F.: Agent-based Retail Competition and Portfolio Optimization in Liberalized Electricity Markets: A Study Involving Real-World Consumers. *Int J Electr Power Energy Syst* 2022;137:107687.
8. Ayón, X., Gruber, J., Hayes, B., Usaola, J., Prodanovic, M.: An optimal day-ahead load scheduling approach based on the flexibility of aggregate demands. *Applied Energy* 2017; 198:1–11.
9. Wei, N., Li, C., Peng, X., Zeng, F., Lu, X.: Conventional models and artificial intelligence-based models for energy consumption forecasting: A review. *Journal of Petroleum Science and Engineering* 2019;181:106187.

10. Koponen, P., Ikäheimo, J., Koskela, J., Brester, C., Niska, H.: Assessing and comparing short term load forecasting performance. *Energies* 2020; 13(8):2054.
11. Algarvio, H.: Multi-step optimization of the purchasing options of power retailers to feed their portfolios of consumers. *Int J Electr Power Energy Syst* 2022;142:108260.
12. Algarvio, H., Lopes, F.: Risk management and bilateral contracts in multi-agent electricity markets. In: Highlights of practical applications of heterogeneous multi-agent systems. Springer Verlag; 2014, p. 297–308.
13. Lopes, F., Algarvio, H., Santana, J.: Agent-based simulation of electricity markets: Risk management and contracts for difference. In: Agent-based modeling of sustainable behaviors. Springer Verlag; 2017, p. 207–25
14. Rodrigues, F., Trindade, A.: Load forecasting through functional clustering and ensemble learning. *Knowl Inf Syst* 2018;57(1):229–44.
15. Algarvio, H.: Retailers' Portfolio of Consumers, Harvard Dataverse, V2, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/WFQ5V0>, [Accessed on 3 June 2022].